

ESTIMATION OF *trans*-ISOOLEIC ACIDS IN HYDROGENATED FATS

BY D. D. NANAVATI, SHARDA DASGUPTA AND J. S. AGGARWAL

The modified Twitchell lead salt-alcohol method of Cocks *et al.* has been found to provide an accurate estimation of *trans*-isoleic acids in hydrogenated fats, taking the infra-red absorption spectrophotometric procedure as the standard.

The quantitative determination of *isoleic* acid contents in partially hydrogenated fats is of great importance because of these acids' contribution to the body of the product at low temperatures. Moore (*J. Soc. Chem Ind.*, 1919, 38, 3207) and Hilditch and Vidyarathi (*Proc. Roy. Soc.* 1929, 122A, 552) have shown that both geometrical and positional isomers are formed in the hydrogenation of alkyl oleates. The American Oil Chemists Society recommended the modified Twitchell lead salt-alcohol method (A.O.C.S. Official Method, Cd. 6-38) for the determination of *isoleic* acids in fatty acid mixtures. Swern *et al.* (*J. Amer. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 27, 17), however, found that by this method the results in most cases differed widely from those obtained by the infra-red spectrophotometric technique. *trans*-Octadecenoic acids are not determined quantitatively by the Twitchell lead salt-alcohol method, the results being low by the latter procedure. Moreover, when large amounts of *cis* acids are present, these are also isolated partially with the solid acid fraction. Jackson and Callen (*ibid.*, 1951, 28, 61) found that the Twitchell method was fairly satisfactory for simple elaidic-oleic acid mixture but afforded very low values with ordinary hydrogenated fat acids. The reason for this failure has been attributed to the increasing solubility of lead *isoleate* with the increase in the number of *trans*-*isoleic* acids. Cocks, Christian and Harding (*Analyst*, 1931, 56, 368) have suggested a modification of the Twitchell method, involving the use of petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in conjunction with the formation of lead salts in alcohol for the more accurate determination of *isoleic* acids in fatty acid mixtures.

Although the infra-red spectrophotometric method has been found to be rapid, specific and accurate for the estimation of *trans*-*isoleic* acids in fatty acid mixtures, it requires special equipment which is not always available. During the investigations on the modification of nickel catalyst for the hydrogenation of oils being carried out in this laboratory, the amounts of *isoleic* acids in various hydrogenated samples of groundnut and cottonseed oils have been determined by the method of Cocks *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). The results have generally been found to be in close agreement with those obtained by the infra-red spectrophotometric method, showing thereby that the method of Cocks *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) may be employed for the accurate determination of *trans*-*isoleic* acids in hydrogenated fats when spectrophotometric procedure is not available.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The hydrogenation of various samples of groundnut and cottonseed oils to a capillary slip point 36-37° was carried out in a laboratory Parr's medium pressure hydrogenation apparatus at different temperatures and pressures. Except where indicated in Table I, the nickel catalyst used was prepared at 460-470°F from nickel formate by wet reduction process in groundnut oil and its concentration varied from 0.05 to 0.30% in different experiments. After the hydrogenation 5 g. decolorising carbon and 5 g. hyflo-supercel were added and the hydrogenated oil was separated by filtration through No. 1 Whatman filter paper.

The fatty acids of the hydrogenated fats were prepared by the usual saponification procedure. Determinations of isooleic acids in the various samples were carried out in duplicate by the method of Cocks *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). These values were checked by the infra-red spectrophotometric method.

A Grubb-Parsons' spectrophotometer of the single beam type with a sodium chloride prism was used for obtaining the infra-red data. Determinations were made using a fixed slit 0.2 mm and at 0.1 mm sodium chloride cell. The fatty acids of hydrogenated oils were examined as solutions of known concentrations in purified carbon disulphide. The base line technique of Wright (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1941, 19, 1) and Heigl, Bell and White (*Anal. Chem.*, 1947, 19, 293) was used for the measurement of optical densities. It has been shown by Rasmusson *et al.* (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1947, 15, 135) and Swern *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) that *trans* mono-unsaturated compounds have a strong characteristic absorption at 10.36 μ unlike *cis* and saturated compounds. A calibration curve (Fig. 1) of elaidic acid (B.D.H.) was obtained by plotting its known concentrations in carbon disulphide against their optical densities which were determined by finding out the percentage absorptions at 10.36 μ . Extinction coefficient, K , has been calculated from the formula $K = d/cl$, where d is the optical density, c is the concentration in g./litre and l is the cell thickness in cm.

FIG. 1

The extinction coefficient (K) for elaidic acid has been found to be 0.593. The extinction coefficients of the acids of hydrogenated fats at 10.36 μ were obtained as

above and from these values and that of pure elaidic acid the percentages of *trans*-isooleic acids in various samples were calculated. For each sample six values were independently taken and the mean results recorded. The percentages of isooleic acids in various samples of hydrogenated groundnut and cottonseed oils, found by both chemical and spectrophotometric methods, are recorded in Tables I and II respectively,

TABLE I

Hydrogenated groundnut oil.

Sr. No.	Conditions of hydrogenation.			<i>trans</i> -Isooleic acids in fatty acids samples		
	% Catlyst.	Temp.	Pressure. (p.s.i.)	Infra-red method.	Cocks' method.	Variation of Cocks' value from infra- red value.
1	Commercial brand vanaspati	I		40.75%	41.22%	1.1%
2		Do	II	32.94	33.70	2.3
3		Do	III	30.20	28.37	6.0
4	0.20 (a)	176-82°	85-90	5.20	4.88	6.1
5	0.20 (b)	"	"	18.50	17.30	6.5
6	0.05	"	"	31.70	31.67	0.1
7	0.10	"	"	29.87	29.71	0.5
8	0.15	"	"	24.98	25.33	1.4
9	0.20	"	"	35.80	35.46	0.9
10	0.25	"	"	24.58	24.47	0.4
11	0.30	"	"	31.50	32.14	2.0
12	0.20	150-55°	"	28.02	28.20	0.6
13	0.20	160-66°	"	25.68	25.90	0.8
14	0.20	176-82°	"	35.80	35.46	0.9
15	0.20	188-93°	"	24.56	24.60	0.2
16	0.20	193-99°	"	26.54	26.60	0.2
17	0.20	201-207°	"	36.48	36.60	0.3
18	0.20	210-15°	"	30.89	30.80	0.3
19	0.20	176-82°	5-10	41.14	40.96	0.4
20	0.20	"	10-15	30.95	30.70	0.8
21	0.20	"	25-30	35.82	35.96	0.4
22	0.20	"	35-40	25.72	26.10	1.5
23	0.20	"	45-50	33.92	33.55	1.1
24	0.20	"	55-60	28.72	27.31	4.9
25	0.20	"	65-70	24.75	25.50	3.0
26	0.20	"	75-80	40.10	37.80	5.8
27	0.20	"	85-90	34.25	35.46	3.5
28	0.20	"	95-100	37.16	37.80	1.7
29	0.20	"	75-90	37.11	37.85	2.0
30	0.20 (c)	"	"	32.99	33.68	2.1
31	0.20 (d)	"	"	33.20	33.63	1.3
32	0.20 (e)	"	"	36.09	36.53	1.2

(a)—Catalyst was prepared at 480°-485°. (b)—Ruffert catalyst used. (c), (d) and (e)—75% of used catalyst from experiments 29, 30 and 31 respectively with 25% of fresh catalyst was employed in each case.

TABLE II

Hydrogenated cottonseed oil.

Sr. No.	% Catalyst.	Temp. = 176-82°. Pressure = 75-90 p.s.i.		
		Infra-red method.	Cocks' method.	Variation of Cocks' value from infra-red value.
1	0.2	42.82%	43.17%	0.8%
2	0.2 (a)	39.97	40.55	1.5
3	0.2 (b)	44.84	44.69	0.3
4	0.2 (c)	46.47	46.51	0.9

(a), (b) and (c)—75% of used catalyst from experiments 1, 2 and 3 respectively with 25% of fresh catalyst was employed in each case.

DISCUSSION

From the data in Tables I and II, it is seen that with the exception of five results (Table I), there is a fair agreement between the amount of *isooleic* acids as determined by infra-red spectroscopic method and by the chemical procedure (Cocks *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) in various samples of hydrogenated fats. Even in the results of five samples, the variations between the two values have not been more than 6.5%. The chances of separation of the lead salts of the various isomers of *cis* mono-ethenoid C_{18} acids, formed as a result of shifting of the double bond of oleic acid or due to hydrogenation of linoleic acid, along with those of *trans-isooleic* acids are greatly minimized because (i) the *cis*-positional isomers are formed much less than the *trans* ones (Allen and Kiess, *J. Amer. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 400) and (ii) the lead salts of the isomeric solid oleic acids have been found by Hilditch and Vidyarathi (*loc. cit.*) closely similar in solubility so that little or no separation results. In fact $\Delta^{8:9}$ and $\Delta^{10:11}$ -octadecenoic acids were found by the latter authors to furnish the soluble lead salts. Further, the data in Tables I and II clearly show that in cases where the results by Cocks' method are higher than the infra-red procedure, the differences are of minor nature and remain within the experimental error.

Therefore the Twitchell lead salt-alcohol procedure, as modified by Cocks *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), may be recommended as an alternative procedure for the determination of *trans-isooleic* acids in the hydrogenated fats where the more accurate infra-red absorption procedure is not available.